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Data ingestion services V2

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.2, “*Data Ingestion Services V2*”, describes the second version of the data ingestion services developed within the ARCFISH project. The project is funded by the Research Council of Norway (RCN), Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT, Portugal), the National Centre for Research and Development (NCBR, Poland), Innovation Fund Denmark (IFD), and the Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS), following the successful evaluation of proposals under the 2023 First Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership Joint Transnational Co-Funded Call.

The deliverable documents the data ingestion services developed during the first 18 months of the ARCFISH project and presents an update to Deliverable D2.1, “*Data Ingestion Services V1*”, which was published after the first 12 months. It extends the previous document by including descriptions of ongoing developments and newly implemented functionalities, linked to specific tasks and activities within the project, and presents selected examples of the data processing and visualisation in the ARCFISH DTO (Blue Insight DTO platform).

ARCFISH is focused in developing a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) supporting sustainable fisheries in the Arctic. The DTO solution, adapted for ARCFISH, is based on the existing Blue Insight platform that seamlessly supports the market segments of the ocean observing value chain of the New Blue Economy (Heslop et al., 2022). The New Blue Economy, also known as the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE), is a concept that promotes sustainable development and conservation of ocean resources for economic, social, and environmental benefits.

In the Arctic, sustainable fisheries focusing on achieving long-term sustainability and resilience of ocean ecosystems and communities is the key to uphold good living conditions for its residents. However, the negative impacts of traditional economic activities such as overfishing, marine pollution, habitat destruction, and climate change have threatened the health and sustainability of the ocean, leading to declining fish stocks, loss of biodiversity, and increased coastal vulnerability to natural disasters.

New data products and services, co-developed with relevant stakeholders, are needed to provide a better basis for decision-making in fisheries planning and management. For example, for Disko Bay, western Greenland, ecosystem indices based on an improved ecosystem model could include monthly spatial maps of zooplankton biomass and production, benthos biomass, shrimp biomass, and upwelling areas. Data collected around Iceland towards the Barents Sea onboard fishing vessels and in seafood processing could be implemented in the DTO to support relevant stakeholders. For the Arctic in general, potential new services could include advanced eLogbooks and spatiotemporal pattern detection and visualisation. For cost-efficiency these services must leverage novel digital technologies such as DTOs to acquire, process, analyse and visualise heterogeneous data from a wide range of sources.

More information on the project can be found at: <https://www.arcfish.eu/>.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AIS	Automatic Identification System
ARC-MFC	Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center
AWE	Automatic Workflow Engine
BGC	Biogeochemical
Blue-Cloud2026	A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Service
CTD	Conductivity, Temperature, and Depth
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTO	Digital Twin of the Ocean
EDITO	European Digital Twin of the Ocean
FCT	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EOSC	European Ocean Science Cloud
GEM	Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring
IFD	Innovation Fund Denmark
ILIAD	Integrated digital solution facilitates access to oceanic data and boosts decision-making
In Situ TAC	Copernicus Marine In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre
INTAROS	Integrated Arctic observation system
NCBR	The National Centre for Research and Development, Poland
NetCDF	Network Common Data Format
NIRD	National Infrastructure for Research Data (Norway)
NMDC	Norwegian Marine Data Centre
NRT	Near Real Time
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPeNDAP	Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol
RANNIS	The Icelandic Centre for Research, Iceland
RCN	Research Council of Norway
SBE	Sustainable Blue Economy
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
THREDDS	Thematic Real-time Environmental Distributed Data Services
TOR	Task Orchestrator Framework
WAM	WAve Model

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

ARCFISH is focused on developing a pilot Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) Platform delivering new data products and services in support of sustainable Arctic fisheries. These data products and services are co-designed with stakeholders in their respective public and private sectors, particularly in the fisheries sector, and used to create products such as ecosystem indices that can be applied in fisheries planning and management. Available data sources and gaps were identified and analysed to fulfil user needs and ingest relevant data into the Blue Insight DTO platform. They include (1) oceanographic data from research vessels, autonomous mobile platforms, fixed buoys, and ships of opportunity such as fishing vessels, (2) met-ice-ocean forecasts and reanalysis from models (e.g., from CMEMS and INTAROS), (3) fisheries management data (e.g., fisheries stocks, species) from ICES and national sources, and (4) reference data (e.g., bathymetry, economic zones, AIS data).

Based on stakeholder needs, a use case for sustainable fisheries will be implemented using the ingested data and tools for generating customised products. The DTO will serve two geographic regions, the west coast of Greenland centred around the rich fishing grounds surrounding Disko Bay, and the region around Iceland, northwards to the Svalbard archipelago and the Barents Sea. Using the compiled data and developed tools, a regional database of climate, environmental, and fisheries data will be created and made available through an open data repository to support sustainable Arctic fisheries. This important asset will contribute to the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) program by providing new data products that can be utilised in DTO platforms to support decision-making in fisheries management, and the Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE).

The Blue Insight Platform developed by Kongsberg Discovery, Norway, will be part of the Digital Twins of the Ocean (DITTO) program of the UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development. As part of DITTO and through engagement with other running Digital Twin projects and initiatives such as EDITO, ILIAD, Blue-Cloud2026 and EOSC, ARCFISH development will follow standards for data exchange and implementation of services and tools in the EU DTO. ARCFISH will prepare training material for using the ARCFISH DTO and organise capacity building events for stakeholders and other SBE projects. Training will be organised in conjunction with project meetings and/or SBEP events. Furthermore, the regional database, developed services and tools, training and promotional material will be promoted through the iAOS portal from INTAROS, a public project website linked to relevant DTO sites, through the ARCFISH website, and dedicated social media channels. ARCFISH results will also be promoted through the partners' extensive network of Arctic observing and data management, digital technologies, capacity building in ocean literacy, stakeholder interaction and fisheries.

1.2. Organisation of the document

The structure of this document is as follows. Chapter 2 provides a short introduction of how data products can be ingested into the Blue Insight digital platform. Chapter 3 presents the ingestion services for in situ data products from research projects, operational services and monitoring programmes in the regions addressed by the two case studies. Chapters 4-6 showcase ingestion of selected data products from ice-ocean models, satellite data, and ecosystem models covering the areas of interest for ARCFISH, while Chapter 7 presents a first set of fishery-dependent and resource management data. The final chapter,

Chapter 8, summarizes the work on preparation of data products for ARCFISH to be fed into WP3 (New data products and regional database) and plans for further enhancement of data products offered through the Blue Insight platform for the ARCFISH community. The document describes the data ingestion services developed in the first 18 months of the ARCFISH project and presents the update of the D2.1 "Data ingestion services V1". The description of ongoing development and new functionalities of the services has been added to the previous document for specific tasks and activities and implemented modifications have been also presented.

2. Short introduction on the ingestion services

Data may enter the digital twin in several ways. Either from measurements made by the project partners, from in-situ sources or from models developed by the project partners in this or other projects.

Blue Insight natively prioritizes support for Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) interfaces, to be more interoperable with other existing digital twin solutions. A large portion of the scientific community also relies on OPeNDAP (Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol), and specifically the THREDDS server implementation for distribution and integration of model and measurement data in NetCDF format (Figure 1). To facilitate THREDDS, Blue Insight has as part of this project extended the data import features with THREDDS integration functionality to avoid reloading existing accessible datasets into the native databases of the twin.

Figure 1. THREDDS Client Integration diagram

OPeNDAP integration will provide efficient access to remote scientific datasets. This integration enhances our ability to work with large volumes of data without the need for local storage or complete file downloads.

The data is loaded in a few simple steps. First the user will locate the appropriate THREDDS server. The common source used in this project is the IAOS portal (<https://portal-intaros.nersc.no/>), and the Meteorological Institute of Norway (<https://thredds.met.no>) but the implementation is not limited to these sources.

From the data loading screen (Figure 2), multiple sources can be accessed. OGC compliant feature APIs, local data in OGC formats (csv, geojson, parquet etc), Cloud Optimized geotiffs (hosted on a cloud server), or OPeNDAP servers.

Figure 2 Data loading screen integrating several sources.

The solution provides a catalogue exploration service and will drill down into the capabilities of the THREDDS catalogue.

Once the appropriate dataset is located, the user will be presented with several choices (Figure 3). The data can be filtered and loaded as points into the scene, the data can be loaded as layers (maps, Figure 4) or the data can be downloaded for further processing through, for instance, the Automatic Workflow Engine (AWE), AWE has replaced the TOR (Task Orchestrator Framework) from earlier deliveries focusing even more on task automation.

Figure 3 Data loader screen presenting multiple options for the user.

Figure 4 Sea ice thickness loaded as layers into the scene. If the data has a time component, it can also replay the time.

3. Ingestion services for in situ oceanographic data

3.1. In situ oceanographic data from IOPAN AREX cruises

The main aim of the long-term AREX program and annual cruises, carried by RV Oceania for the last 37 years in the Nordic Seas and Fram Strait, is to study processes responsible for changing ocean climate and marine ecosystems in the sub-Arctic and Arctic regions. To achieve this goal a large-scale domain, covering the poleward flow of Atlantic water in the eastern Nordic Seas and Fram Strait, has been selected for annually repeated ship-borne measurements. Most of the regularly repeated stations are distributed along several zonal sections, crossing the continental shelf break, and extending towards the deep basins. On the eastern side, the AREX oceanographic sections are limited by the Barents Sea shelf break and the shelf area west and north of Svalbard. To the west, the sections cross the Arctic Front, located above the system of underwater ridges and limiting the extent of Atlantic water in the Nordic Seas.

CTD data (temperature and salinity profiles) from AREX cruises in 2000-2024 and derived data products including e.g. mean properties of Atlantic water or surface layer, mixed layer depth, or integrated ocean heat content have been prepared for ingestion into Blue Insight. Temperature and salinity profiles from AREX cruises can be uploaded into Blue Insight directly from text files in CSV format or from netCDF files after conversion into GeoJSON format. Data from AREX cruises in CSV and netCDF formats is available via the IOPAN OPeNDAP server (Hyrax). In the next step, the gridded fields based on station data will be prepared for visualization in Blue Insight.

Visualization of the mean temperature and salinity of Atlantic water layer, calculated from AREX observations, is shown using Map (Ocean View) and 3D Map functionalities of Blue Insight. (Figure 5 - Figure 7). In Ocean View individual data sets for each cruise have been uploaded as separate layers which enables selecting one or more visible layers for comparison between years. In 3D Map temperature and salinity data and derived quantities have been uploaded as one file for all years (the collated file has been prepared in the first step; all data are shown on Figure 5 and Figure 6). Data from individual years (cruises) can be seen using time filtering functionality of 3D Map (Figure 7).

Figure 5 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations occupied in 2019 and 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Note that the colour scale is different for each year.

Figure 6 Mean salinity of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for stations 2023 using Blue Insight Ocean View. Other years can be displayed by switching different layers on/off Note that the colour scale is different for each year.

Figure 7 Mean temperature of the Atlantic layer measured during the AREX cruises and shown for all stations occupied in 2000-2023 using Blue Insight 3D Map. For each station the full set of associated variables can be displayed by selection the station dot with the cursor. Time filter in the lower bottom corner shows time of measurements and allows for selecting a subset of data. The background colour shows ocean bathymetry (GEBCO), available as a separate layer in 3D Map.

3.2. In situ oceanographic data from Copernicus MDS (CORA analysed fields, CORA Near Real Time dataset)

Copernicus Marine In Situ Thematic Assembly Centre (In Situ TAC) products: INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_MY_013_052 and INSITU_GLO_PHY_TS_OA_NRT_013_002 were generated by the Coriolis team (the Data Centre and the Research & Development team) in Brest, France, providing global Temperature and Salinity observation datasets and objective analysis gridded fields at different time scales. The second one is a Near Real Time product (NRT) while the first one (also called CORA Analysed fields, see Cabanes et al., 2013 and Szekely et al., 2019) is a reanalysis of these NRT datasets in delayed mode.

Links and time ranges for both CORA Optimal Reanalyses:

- CORA DM data set: <https://doi.org/10.17882/46219>, 01/01/1960–01/06/2024
- CORA NRT data set: <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-0003>, 01/01/2023–01/10/2025

The system is based on a statistical analysis method (objective analysis, Bretherton et al., 1976) developed and maintained at LOPS (Laboratoire d’Océanographie Physique et Spatial, Gaillard et al., 2012): the In Situ Analysis System (ISAS). It is performed on the datasets extracted from the Coriolis database for data quality control and producing gridded scalar fields. This system allows presenting a synthesis and a validation of the dataset, providing a support for localized experience (cruises), providing a validation source for operational models, observing seasonal cycle and inter-annual variability. It is the In Situ Objective analysis operational nominal product for the Global Ocean. The dataset contains data from different types of instruments: mainly Argo floats (including ITP), CTD, XBT and XCTD, moorings, drifting buoys and sea mammals.

The geographical selections/subsets of the Copernicus products were downloaded with use of python scripts/Jupyter Notebooks in netCDF format and were further transformed into GeoJSON format. These output files can be accessed via THREDDS server implementation included in the Blue Insight platform.

In the example below monthly fields of temperature (Figure 8) and salinity (Figure 9) at depth of 1m were ingested into the Blue Insight and presented as points with colour indicating the spatial variability in January 2024. In the further steps depth will be integrated as additional dimension to the geoJSON files. Currently, for each depth level datasets were loaded separately but can be displayed together (Figure 10). Currently the used projection is WGS84 (EPSG:4326), it can be switched to polar stereographic (EPSG:3413 or EPSG:3995).

Figure 8 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Temperature in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.

Figure 9 CORA NRT temperature and salinity data at depth of 1m loaded as layers into the scene. Salinity in January 2024 is displayed. The data has a time component and can be shown for other months of 2024.

Figure 10 CORA NRT temperature data at depth of 1m and 300m loaded as layers into the scene. The datasets have a time component and are displayed for April 2024.

The GUI functionality allows users to interact with a digital device using visual elements like windows, icons, and menus instead of text commands, with a pointing device or touch, making access to the environmental data that has a potential impact on the marine life more user-friendly and intuitive for a wide audience, e.g. stakeholders. To secure the use of all necessary components and libraries, these GUIs will be further included in the Docker containers.

Two Jupyter notebooks (and Python script) GUIs were developed to select and display the CORA DM and CORA NRT (which contains the recent observations) subsets in the northern North Atlantic in the NetCDF-4 format, by clicking on visual components: the list of accessible variables (in this example, temperature TEMP, or practical salinity PSAL, or both, with monthly time resolution, at all available depth levels), in the desired area limited by the latitude and longitude range, for a selected time period, specific for each CORA product, respectively (Figures 11 & 12). These GUIs are like the one available on the Copernicus website; nevertheless, they can be used as standalone components transported via Docker container into AWE.

Another Jupyter notebook GUI is dedicated to choosing and easily plotting the required variable (temperature TEMP or practical salinity PSAL) from the retrieved CORA dataset subset (here with monthly time resolution, but it can be adjusted for a higher resolution in the next GUI versions), at a selected date and depth level corresponding to the data available in the input NetCDF file. This GUI functionality allows for interactive selection and plotting of the variable, depth level, time and geographical range, with colour maps, colour bars and colour limits switching automatically depending on the chosen variable (Figures 13 & 14). The goal of this GUI is to preselect the CORA dataset for further export to a format acceptable by the Blue Insight platform.

ARCFISH data ingestion services - loading CORA DM monthly dataset

Choose start and end times at least partly within this range: 01/01/1960, 00:00→01/06/2024, 00:00

Longitude E: -50.00 - 50.00

Latitude N: 55.00 - 85.00

Start Date:

End Date:

Variables:

```

Dataset loaded and saved successfully:
<xarray.Dataset> Size: 451MB
Dimensions:   (depth: 187, latitude: 300, longitude: 201, time: 10)
Coordinates:
  * depth      (depth) float32 748B 1.0 3.0 5.0 10.0 ... 5.3e+03 5.4e+03 5.5e+03
  * latitude   (latitude) float64 2kB 55.1 55.2 55.3 55.4 ... 84.8 84.9 85.0
  * longitude  (longitude) float64 2kB -50.0 -49.5 -49.0 ... 49.0 49.5 50.0
  * time       (time) datetime64[ns] 80B 2022-01-01 2022-02-01 ... 2022-10-01
Data variables:
  TEMP        (time, depth, latitude, longitude) float32 451MB ...
Attributes: (12/21)
  Conventions:          CF-1.4
  analysis_name:        OA_CORA5.2_
  comment:              V8.0 reference climatology and analysis parameters
  creation_date:        20240604T073040L
  data_manager:         Tanguy Szekely
  easternmost_longitude: 179.5
  ...
  source:               ISAS-V8
  southernmost_latitude: -77.0105
  start_date:           2023-12-15
  stop_date:            2023-12-15
  title:                Global Ocean - Coriolis Observation Re-Analysis C...
  westernmost_longitude: -180
    
```

Figure 11. Jupyter Notebook GUI for selecting and loading CORA DM data subset in the North Atlantic.

The final Jupyter Notebook GUI is dedicated to exporting the retrieved NetCDF-4 file with the CORA subset to CSV format (or GeoJSON in the next GUI version) that can be used directly in Blue Insight’s Map and 3D Map (Figure 15). If the selected geographical region is large, the time and depth ranges are wide, resulting in a time-consuming export process. Therefore, a progress bar is included in this GUI to indicate user how much more time it may take.

In the last two GUIs (plotting and exporting of files), paths to the input NetCDF files and output CSV files are fixed; however, an additional function needs to be added that allows users to choose the file paths themselves. It depends on how the GUIs are used and whether these files can be stored locally or on the Blue Insight server.

An example of the exported CSV file with the CORA NRT subset is shown in the following figure (Figure 16). The data in a preselected geographical region is loaded into the Blue Insight scene, and one of the exported variables (PSAL) is displayed with filters built for additional time and depth selection. The representation of the masked values (here, data on the land) could possibly be improved upon, but this may require corrections in the exporting GUI code itself.

ARCFISH data ingestion services - loading CORA NRT monthly dataset

Choose start and end times at least partly within this range: 01/01/2023, 00:00 → 01/10/2025, 00:00

Longitude E: -50.00 - 50.00

Latitude N: 55.00 - 85.00

Start Date:

End Date:

Variables:

```

Dataset loaded and saved successfully:
<xarray.Dataset> Size: 451MB
Dimensions:   (depth: 187, latitude: 300, longitude: 201, time: 10)
Coordinates:
  * depth      (depth) float32 748B 1.0 3.0 5.0 10.0 ... 5.3e+03 5.4e+03 5.5e+03
  * latitude   (latitude) float64 2kB 55.1 55.2 55.3 55.4 ... 84.8 84.9 85.0
  * longitude  (longitude) float64 2kB -50.0 -49.5 -49.0 ... 49.0 49.5 50.0
  * time       (time) datetime64[ns] 80B 2025-01-01 2025-02-01 ... 2025-10-01
Data variables:
  TEMP        (time, depth, latitude, longitude) float32 451MB ...
Attributes: (12/21)
  Conventions:          CF-1.6
  analysis_name:        OA_NRTOAGL01
  comment:              V8.0 reference climatology and analysis parameters
  creation_date:        20241125T032529
  data_manager:         Thierry.Carval@ifremer.fr
  easternmost_longitude: 179.5
  ...
  source:               ISAS-V8
  southernmost_latitude: -77.0105
  start_date:           2024-10-15
  stop_date:            2024-10-15
  title:                Global Ocean - Coriolis Analysis - Near Real Time
  westernmost_longitude: -180
    
```

Figure 12. Jupyter Notebook GUI for selecting and loading CORA NRT data subset in the North Atlantic.

ARCFISH Data Ingestion Services - Plotting CORA DM Monthly Field

Select variable, date, depth, latitude and longitude

Choose a time: 01/01/1960 → 01/06/2024

Variable: ▾

Depth (m):

Select Date: 📅

Longitude E:

Latitude N:

Figure 13. Jupyter Notebook GUI for selecting and plotting CORA DM variable (here TEMP) data subset in the North Atlantic.

ARCFISH data ingestion services - plotting CORA NRT monthly field at chosen depth and location

Select variable, date, depth, latitude and longitude

Choose start and end times at least partly within this range: 01/01/2023 → 01/10/2025

Variable: ▼

Depth (m):

Select Date: 📅

Longitude E: -

Latitude N: -

Figure 14. Jupyter Notebook GUI for selecting and plotting CORA NRT variable (here PSAL) data subset in the North Atlantic.

ARCFISH data ingestion services - exporting CORA NRT monthly field to CSV

Select latitude, longitude, time range, depth, and variables

Choose start and end month within this range: Jan 2023 → Oct 2025 (depends on the input file)

Variables:

Time Range:

Depth Range:

Latitude N:

Longitude E:

Progress:

Data exported to csv/CORA_temp_sal_2025_north_atlantic.csv

Figure 15. Jupyter Notebook GUI for exporting CORA NRT data subset in the North Atlantic to a CSV file.

Figure 16. CORA NRT data subset exported to a CSV file and loaded to a scene in the BI. Floating insets show individual values for coordinates and variables at two selected points and additionally (in red and green) differences between them.

For accessing and plotting CORA data subsets, Docker Images and their running versions, Docker Containers can be used. The dedicated Docker Images contain: Docker file, requirements.txt file with all necessary libraries, Python script with code, and editable .env file with credentials required by the data provider (<https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/> - see how to register to obtain these credentials). An example of a Docker file from Docker Image is shown in Figure 17, an example of a variable request to be passed via the .env file is shown in Figure 18.

The building and running of Docker files can be done by two code lines in the Terminal window while inside the app folder:

```
docker build -t cora-plot:latest .
```

```
docker run --rm --env-file .env -v "$(pwd)/work":/app/work cora-plot:latest
```

The downloaded CORA dataset in the NetCDF-4 format is stored in the 'work' directory, similarly as .png images with plotted T and S variables.

In the next steps, the data will be stored in CSV format and further imported into the Blue Insight platform via AWE. For the NRT data AWE will enable regular updates of the Blue Insight input without a need of manual fetching of CORA subsets.

The screenshot shows a web interface for a Docker build. The build name is 'cora_plot_subset_docker_app' and it is in a 'Completed' status. Below the build details, there are tabs for 'Info', 'Source', 'Logs', and 'History'. The 'Source' tab is active, displaying the Dockerfile content for the 'amd64' platform. The Dockerfile instructions are as follows:

```

1 FROM python:3.11-slim
2
3 WORKDIR /app
4
5 RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends \
6     ca-certificates build-essential wget gfortran libnetcdf-dev && rm -rf /var/lib/apt/lists/*
7
8 COPY requirements.txt /app/requirements.txt
9 RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r /app/requirements.txt
10
11 COPY . /app
12 RUN mkdir -p /app/work && useradd --create-home --shell /bin/bash appuser && chown -R appuser:appuser /app
13 USER appuser
14
15 CMD ["python", "/app/run_subset_and_plot.py"]
16
    
```

Figure 17. Example of Docker file required to run Docker container focusing on accessing, sub-setting and plotting CORA data.

```

# Read env vars (fallback defaults for example)
CMEMS_USER = os.environ.get('CMEMS_USER')
CMEMS_PASS = os.environ.get('CMEMS_PASS')
if not CMEMS_USER or not CMEMS_PASS:
    raise SystemExit("Set CMEMS_USER and CMEMS_PASS environment variables")

LON_MIN = float(os.environ.get('LON_MIN', -180))
LON_MAX = float(os.environ.get('LON_MAX', 180))
LAT_MIN = float(os.environ.get('LAT_MIN', -90))
LAT_MAX = float(os.environ.get('LAT_MAX', 90))
START_DATE = os.environ.get('START_DATE', '2020-01-01T00:00:00')
END_DATE = os.environ.get('END_DATE', '2020-01-02T00:00:00')
OUT_DIR = os.environ.get('OUT_DIR', '/app/work')
OUT_FILE = os.environ.get('OUT_FILE', 'cora_subset.nc')
    
```

Figure 18. Excerpt from the Python script that shows the environmental variables necessary to obtain the CORA subset inside the running Docker container

3.3. In situ oceanographic data from Argo floats in the use case regions

Argo float data were integrated through the OPeNDAP service described in Chapter 2 which enables downloading of data files from individual Argo floats.

Additionally, a dedicated ingestion service has been developed for extracting and updating the most recent Argo data for the specific region (e.g. defined for ARCFISH use cases) and further processing to prepare the aggregated csv file, ready for ingestion into Blue Insight. By default, the Argo datasets fetched by the ingestion service include all Argo core data (pressure, temperature, and salinity) for the period from 01.01.2020 (the start date can be adjusted) to the current date and time and for the predefined depth range. The ingestion service is partially based on the `argopy` Python package which enables access to Argo data from different sources, including the daily updated Ifremer ERDDAP server (default option), any of the 3 official GDAC online servers (the Ifremer https and ftp and the US https), or Argovis server (<https://github.com/euroargodev/argopy>, Maze et al., 2020). Data can be fetched at the different level of quality control but to assure the highest quality of data ingested into Blue insight, the data are downloaded in the research mode, only preserving only data of the highest quality (standard and expert modes are also available).

Due to the large amount of data from the region of interest, Argo data are fetched using parallelisation (fetching chunks of independent data simultaneously) and caching functionalities of `argopy`. Requested data from all individual floats within the specified region and time frame are downloaded as one aggregated data set (a collection of data points). Subsequently, all data points are transformed to profiles and interpolated onto the standard pressure levels with the step of 10 dbar, allowing for consistent visualisation in Blue Insight. Finally, the data set for ingestion is exported to the csv file preserving only the relevant coordinates (time, longitude, latitude, pressure) and associated variables (temperature, salinity). The data fetcher part of the Python script for Argo data ingestion is shown on Figure 19.

```

argopy.set_options(mode='research')
box = [lon_min, lon_max, lat_min, lat_max, pres_min, pres_max+50, time_start, time_end]
f = DataFetcher(parallel=True, progress=True).region(box)
ds = f.to_xarray()
ds.argo

```

4m 59.4s Python

■ Queued
■ Downloading netcdf from the erddap
■ Formatting xarray dataset
■ Callback
■ Failed or No Data
■ Success

Succeed in Merging chunks of xarray dataset (100% processed)

Final post-processing of the merged dataset ...

```

<xarray.Dataset.argo>
This is a collection of Argo points
N_POINTS(1970376) ~ N_PROF(14993) x N_LEVELS(251)

```

Figure 19 Section of the Python script for Argo data ingestion, responsible for data fetcher using parallelisation.

The csv file with pre-processed Argo data is loaded into Blue Insight either as a local file or (in future) from the cloud or OPeNDAP server. In the next steps, Python scripts with data fetcher and preprocessor will be dockerized and the automated workflow to update the Blue Insight input file with pre-processed Argo data on a regular basis will be implemented using AWE.

Visualisation functionalities of Blue Insight allow filtering the entire data set along different coordinates (one or more) and selection of plotted variables. Since the prepared Argo data set includes variables interpolated onto standard levels (in the example, in the layer 0-200 m with 10 m step), filtering can be used to display all values at the selected level (as shown on Figure 20 with surface temperatures plotted for the entire period). Using additional filter along the time axis allows to plot all data points at the selected depth (or depth range) within the selected time window (as shown on Figure 21 with salinity values at the 10 dbar level filtered for the year 2024). The time filter shown on the bottom insert of Figure 21 enables to change (move) the time window dynamically, playing temporal evolution of the selected variable. Comparison between two fields (two variables) is also possible using a double window setup (not shown). Different background fields (not only bathymetry but also e.g. ice coverage or location of the ice edge) can be also displayed on the maps.

In the next steps similar ingestions service will be also complemented for the Argo BGC (biogeochemical) data which can be fetched from the Argo GDACs. While the amount of available BGC measurements from Argo floats is significantly lower than for the CoreArgo measurements (temperature and salinity), the BGC observations can provide a valuable environmental background for Arctic fisheries.

Figure 20 Temperature data at the surface (at the standard level of 0 dbar) from all Argo profiles collected in the Iceland region in the period 1.01.2020-4.02.2026, ingested into Blue Insight and shown with bathymetry in the background.

Figure 21 Salinity at the standard level of 10 dbar from all Argo profiles collected in the Iceland region in the period 1.01.2020-4.02.2026, ingested into Blue Insight filtered to show only data from 2024.

3.4. In situ oceanographic data downloaded from GEM

Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) is an integrated monitoring and long-term research programme on ecosystems and climate change effects and feedback in the Arctic (<https://g-e-m.dk/>). Since 1995 the programme has established a coherent and integrated understanding of the functioning of ecosystems in a highly variable climate, which is based upon a comprehensive, long-term inter-disciplinary data collection carried out by Danish and Greenlandic monitoring and research institutions.

The GEM Programme puts around 75 scientists in the field annually to collect data on ecosystem and climate change in Greenland. The database currently covers data from monitoring programmes from Zackenberg (1995-), Kobbefjord at Nuuk (2007-) and Disko (2017-). The well over 1000 parameters are freely available via the GEM Database and used by GEM participants and external scientists to produce scientific papers, scientific assessments, advisory reports, etc.

In Disko Bay, the Arctic station is on the Disko Island in central west Greenland (Figure 22). The location is characterized by a low Arctic, coastal climate with some of the world's largest icebergs drifting by. In the MarineBasis folder, under GEM, measurements from cruise and monitoring stations in Disko Bay can be found and downloaded. Data includes CTD measurements of salinity and temperature, Chlorophyll a, nutrients (NO₃, NO₂, NH₄, Si, PO₄), pH, dissolved inorganic carbon, suspended particulate matter concentration and macroalgae growth.

Figure 22. Map showing the location of the Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (GEM) station in Disko Bay, Greenland (yellow point)

As an example, temperature and salinity measurements from the Disko Bay cruises in 2018-2024 have been ingested into Blue Insight. The data sets retrieved from the GEM data base include the following records:

- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2018, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 9c8590bd-e3fd-4fbc-8e44-91f02ac53b9f] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/75KS-G922>

- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2019, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 96f92d6b-d114-4897-82de-2e10c7a81772] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/VB94-Y512>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2020, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: e8bac97e-ef5b-4f92-83de-f1ed2c7b5d49] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/MFOH-G023>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2022, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 9ede561d-0808-46c1-8bf2-8c48c262eb4d] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/06Y3-CY76>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2023, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: de40fe63-78ab-4565-817d-97814741c398] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/CXGE-A291>
- Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring (2025). MarineBasis Disko - Water column - Disko Bay Cruise 2024, CTD measurements (Version 1.0). [Data set] [Download ID: 19fccf13-94f0-4873-9bc4-0c23ded2e601] [CC-BY-SA-4.0]. Greenland Ecosystem Monitoring. <https://doi.org/10.17897/45WA-6G76>

For the upload and visualisation in Blue Insight, the original data files in text format have been converted into GeoJSON format with reformatting geographical coordinates into uniform format (decimal degrees) and selecting relevant variables from the source data files (date, depth, temperature, and salinity for the example shown on Figures 23 and 24). In addition to creating individual GeoJSON files for each year, the integrated temperature and salinity data from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 have been collated in one GeoJSON object, allowing to upload all records simultaneously into Blue Insight.

The data conversion tool can be automated through Blue Insight's AWE, and relevant data conversion scripts will be published in the [ARCFISH Zenodo community](#) at the end of the project. Data products like the converted data from the GEM database will be uploaded to the OGC Feature API of Blue Insight for simplification of the data loading process, this provides a standardized interface for sharing in other OGC Feature compatible digital twin projects.

Figure 23. Visualisation of temperature at the depth of 10 m from all GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018-2024 in the Blue Insight. Data from all cruises have been collated into one GeoJSON file. Details for each station can be displayed to show measurement date, depth (while the GeoJSON file includes all measured depths, a single depth can be extracted with a user-defined filter), and measured variables (temperature and salinity).

Figure 24. Visualisation of salinity at the depth of 10 m from GEM cruises in Disko Bay in 2018 and in 2024 in the Blue Insight. Each year of the cruise data is uploaded as a separate layer what allows to display a single year or a combination of different years at the same map. Note that salinity colour scale is different for each year, this will be unified in future version of Blue Insight.

4. Ingestion services for met-ice-ocean model products

4.1. CMEMS Topaz forecast products

A forecast of ice-ocean parameters for the Arctic is produced on a daily basis by the Copernicus Marine Services, for a 10-day period. The forecast is generated by the TOPAZ5 model developed by NERSC and run operationally by the Marine Arctic Monitoring and Forecasting Center (ARC-MFC) operated by the Meteorological Institute of Norway. The forecast contains a number of key ice-ocean parameters such as ocean temperature (Figure 25), salinity, sea ice thickness, sea ice area fraction, and uses a 100-member EnKF assimilation scheme.

ARC-MFC provides access to the TOPAZ5 forecasts through OPeNDAP, enabling selection of specific parameters and sub-setting (in space and time). This allows ingestion of chosen parameters for a given area and time period into Blue Insight. The TOPAZ5 forecasts provide a 10-day forecast of physical ocean parameters and include sea ice parameters generated by the CICEv5.1 model. Data assimilation is done weekly to produce a 7-day ensemble average of the forecast. ARC-MFC provides hourly, 6-hours, daily and monthly mean fields for the TOPAZ5 forecasts. All forecasts are provided in NetCDF-4 format.

NERSC has implemented a data ingestion service extracting TOPAZ5 forecasts from CMEMS, merging the daily forecasts into a 10-day time series and preparing the time series in NetCDF format for ingestion into Blue Insight. The data ingestion service has been implemented in the AWE (Figure 26). The service can be configured to read specific parameters, e.g., sea surface temperature and ocean currents, and define one or more areas of interest. The selected parameters are extracted for the specified area(s), and a NetCDF group is created to hold the data for each area. Parameters needed to plot the forecast on a map are also included in the resulting NetCDF file.

CMEMS makes a new forecast available on a daily basis at a specified time (00:30 UTC) according to its Product User Manual (Ali et al., 2025). The TOPAZ5 extraction service uses the trigger function of AWE to start the workflow at a given time every day. The service is currently set up to start at 00:30 UTC to ensure that a new forecast is available before the service is started. The service consists of three main steps: (1) The data access URL is set up using the current date, (2) The selected parameters and area(s) of interest defined by the service input parameters are extracted and downloaded, and (3) the downloaded files are combined into a single file constituting a time series of forecasted parameters for the next 10 days.

Figure 25. Visualisation of sea surface temperature forecast from the TOPAZ5 model in Blue Insight, including trawling activity data from the Brim fishery, marked as short lines in the visualization.

netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

← Back Copy ID Export Launch Flow

Flow Summary

Flow ID: netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine | Tasks: 3 | Inputs Required: 0 variables

Recent Runs Refresh View All

- 9475d2e48a7b467e817d616b8757f0a7 | 12/01/2026, 01:30:00 | TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 | Completed
- 5555265a41bd4b5caacbd785886b7ada | 11/01/2026, 01:30:00 | TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 | Completed
- 4cd9da1de1804ac78495700e4c3084d4 | 10/01/2026, 01:30:00 | TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 | Completed
- 83cb2e6a75084b9a9a634bd9f837d316 | 09/01/2026, 01:30:00 | TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 | Completed
- 52172e4c3120434a9ba8c27ae78499fa | 08/01/2026, 01:30:00 | TimeTriggered-opendap_imported_1762182372749 | Completed

Flow Configuration

Flow Name: netcdf_opendap_topaz | Tag: 0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

Full Flow ID: netcdf_opendap_topaz:0.3.0_imported_1760109001410_testingcombine

Tasks

- Get names for topaz filelink (dockerContainer)
- Filter and download netcdf file using openDAP (dockerContainer)
- Combine newly created netCDF files (dockerContainer)

Figure 26. Screenshot of the TOPAZ5 extraction service running in the AWE at a given time every day (00:30 UTC). The time shown in the screenshot is in local time (CET), but the workflow specification defines the trigger time in UTC to ensure the service is run at the appropriate time regardless of changes in local time (e.g. summer time).

4.2. CMEMS Wind-Wave forecast product

The Copernicus Marine Service produces forecasts of surface wind and wave conditions in the Arctic using the Wave Model (WAM). The forecasts are generated twice per day at 3 km resolution and provide one-hourly 10-day forecast and one-hourly 5-day forecast. The WAM model provides more than 20 parameters, of which significant wave height (Figure 27), peak period and mean direction are the most commonly used. Surface winds and boundary wave spectra from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and tidal currents and ice from the ARC MFC forecasts (Sea Ice concentration and thickness) were used as forcing fields for the WAM model.

WAM forecasts are provided in NetCDF-4 format and are accessible from the ARC-MFC through OPeNDAP. This allows for sub-setting in space and time, as well as selecting only specific parameters, for visualisation in Blue Insight. Other data, such as trawler paths, can be overlaid on WAM forecasts (Figure 27).

NERSC has implemented a data ingestion service extracting WAM forecasts from CMEMS, merging the daily forecasts into a 10-day time series and preparing the time series in NetCDF format for ingestion into Blue Insight. The data ingestion service has been implemented in the AWE (Figure 28). The WAM service can be configured to read specific parameters, e.g., sea surface temperature and ocean currents, and define one or more areas of interest. The selected parameters are extracted for the specified area(s), and a NetCDF group is created to hold the data for each area. Parameters needed to plot the forecast on a map are also included in the resulting NetCDF file.

CMEMS makes a new WAM forecast available twice a day, at 06:00 UTC and 18:00 UTC according to its Product User Manual (Saetra et al., 2024). The WAM extraction service uses the trigger function of AWE to start the workflow at a given time every day. The service is currently set up to start at 05:15 UTC and 17:15 UTC to ensure that a new forecast is available before the service is started. The WAM service is structured in a similar manner to the TOPAZ5 service, and consists of three main steps: (1) The data access URL is set up using the current date, (2) The selected parameters and area(s) of interest defined by the service input parameters are extracted and downloaded, and (3) the downloaded files are combined into a single file constituting a time series of forecasted parameters for the next 10 days.

Figure 27. Visualisation of significant wave height forecast from WAM model in Blue Insight.

Figure 28. Screenshot of the WAM extraction service running in the AWE two times a day, at 05:15 UTC and 17:15 UTC, to generate a time series of selected parameters for the next 10 days and 5 days respectively.

4.3. Overlaying model products in the 3D Scene builder

The primary data ingestion method in this project is through the OPeNDAP integration described in Chapter 2. However Blue Insight also provides a 3D scene builder, and the capacity to ingest relatively large datasets as points to enable filtering features. Figure 29 illustrates how two model data sets can be visualised on top of each other in Blue Insight.

Figure 29. Model forecasts integrated into the Blue Insight 3D Scene builder. Here illustrated by the Arctic Subpolar gyre sTate Estimate (ASTE) and the Disko Bay model datasets.

5. Data ingestion services for remote sensing data

Satellites play an increasingly important role in ocean sensing, and a number of datasets are available through open sources as comparisons to ground truth collected by cruises, floats or moorings.

5.1. Ocean parameters from satellite remote sensing

Remote ocean sensing is primarily restricted to surface observation, but can be organized into three main categories.

- Blue Ocean, meaning physical ocean characteristics like:
 - Sea surface Temperature (SST)
 - Sea level anomaly
 - Ocean currents
 - Wave height and Sea State
- White Ocean, meaning sea-ice concentration and drift.
- Green Ocean, meaning biogeochemical in terms of Chlorophyll concentrations, algae blooms and primary production.

As data are aggregated and modelled using standard formats they can be combined with in-situ data to provide context and background information. Important sources of data are for instance the Sentinel-3, Sentinel-6 satellites and services like Red Tide Algae Detection system by Kongsberg Satellite Services.

5.2. Wave height from satellite remote sensing

As an example of how these sensors can be integrated, we have included a dataset from Copernicus, based on the wave data detector of the Sentinel 6 satellite. This is just an example of how these types of data can be included into digital twins as long as they are delivered on standard formats. In Figure 30 we

have integrated the Copernicus wave data (WAVE_GLO_PHY_SWH_L3_NRT_014_001) product from the Sentinel-6 satellite as data points.

Figure 30 Integration of Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service (CMEMS) wave data into Blue Insight.

6. Ingestion services for ecosystem model products

Aarhus University has a coupled hydrodynamic-biogeochemical model covering the greater Disko Bay area in west Greenland (Møller et al. 2023, Larsen et al. 2020). The 3D model is implemented in the unstructured marine model framework FlexSem (<https://marweb.bios.au.dk/flexsem>). It has a semi-circular open boundary towards the Baffin Bay, where it is forced by interpolated data from the HYCOM and pan-Arctic “A20” models. It includes meteorological, ice-cover and freshwater runoff forcings. The model has a horizontal resolution varying between 2 km in the inner part to 15 km near the open boundary and has been run for the period 2004–2018 (Møller et al. 2023).

As part of the ARCFISH data ingestion service, model data output from the setup has been transferred to Kongsberg Discovery to be included in the ARCFISH DTO (e.g. Figure 31). AU has provided an integrated C++ and Python API to read the binary native format that stores the unstructured model output and examples of how to read, interpret and present the time varying unstructured 3D data. AU has provided 3D monthly values of temperature, salinity, chlorophyll, primary production, net primary production, light attenuation (Kd), nitrate, phosphate, microzooplankton production, and mesozooplankton production for 2017. The data set was extended with all years from 2004 to 2018. A shrimp larvae module is under development in WP3 and data will be uploaded in the next version.

Figure 31. Disco Bay model integrated into the Blue Insight environment.

7. Ingestion services for fishery-dependent and resource management data

Blue whiting is a small cod fish of great importance for the Icelandic economy. It has historically been used for production of fish meal, for production of aquaculture feed, and fish oil, or in some instances for human consumption. Recent industry trials have shown great potential for further value creation from blue whiting, providing an opportunity for processing the fish for human consumption.

In the first meeting with Brim and TrackWell, it was clear that the fishing company was mostly interested in pelagic species in connection with the digital twin. Especially blue whiting, where the fishing grounds can be difficult to locate, where the species prefers open seas and deep waters. During their lifecycle, blue whiting exhibit seasonal migratory patterns. In the summer months, they are commonly found in deeper waters in the North but during the spawning season, which usually peaks between March and April, they usually migrate to shallower continental shelf areas to reproduce.

Fishing companies are interested in knowing the best location to fish at any given time. Blue whiting is constantly on the move, and it can be a challenge for captains to locate the fish schools. Environmental factors such as salinity, temperature and zooplankton availability can influence the distribution and abundance of blue whiting. A combination of VMS data and fishing data (e.g. catch information) with other relevant data (e.g. ecosystem and resource management data) can have huge potential for stakeholders (e.g. fishing companies, research communities, resource managers, and surveillance sectors). Below are some examples of data integration into the Blue Insight from different fisheries data sources (e.g. Figures 32, 33 and 34).

Figure 32. Vessel movement and trawl data from Trackwell displayed in Blue Insight.

Blue Insight gives the capability for replaying data from specific datasets, or to set filters on specific datatypes to isolate events relevant to the dataset. For instance, isolate all vessel movements at trawling speed, but filter away all data performed at transport speed, as illustrated in Figure 33.

Figure 33. Replay functionality displaying the fishing vessel movement.

Multiple datasets can be included at once to create an overview of the situation in the area, or to correlate fisheries and ocean production scenarios. The combination of multiple datasets can be seen in Figure 34.

Figure 34. The combination of ecosystem modelling and fisheries data.

8. Summary and next steps

During the first 18 months of the ARCFISH project, partners have prepared selected data sets and started to ingest these in the Blue Insight digital platform. This includes several in situ oceanographic data sets and gridded observational data products, forecasts from different ice-ocean and ecosystem models, examples of remote sensing products, as well as sample data from the fisheries sectors. Data ingestion has leveraged the capabilities of Blue Insight to import data from standard formats (e.g. CSV, GeoJSON, GeoTIFF) and the ability to read data through the OPeNDAP standard protocol to enable sub-setting of large datasets. The datasets have been visualised using the 2D Ocean Viewer and the 3D Scene builder components of Blue Insight, where reference data of global bathymetry and regular map data are pre-loaded and can be used as background layers.

Selected in situ data products from environmental monitoring programmes (AREX and GEM), large scale observing networks (Argo), and operational services (NRT and analysed fields from Copernicus MDS) were ingested in Blue Insight. Plans for extending these data products include, among others, gridded fields based on station data from AREX cruises, biogeochemical and optical data from GEM, and in situ BGC data profiles from Argo floats. The data conversion tool for fetching the updated data from available repositories (e.g. GEM database or Argo GDACs) can be automated through Blue Insight’s AWE (Automatic Workflow Environment) framework, and relevant data conversion scripts will be published on Zenodo at the end of the project.

Examples of forecasts from three met-ice-ocean models were integrated, including two forecasts of physical ice-ocean parameters from CMEMS, and a reanalysis of ice-ocean parameters from the University of Texas. The CMEMS TOPAZ5 and WAM model forecasts are publicly available and provided through the OPeNDAP protocol in NetCDF-4 format. This allows for direct integration in Blue Insight through its current ingestion services. The OPeNDAP access to CMEMS model products will also be used to generate new data products based on available model forecasts and reanalyses for the two case study regions in ARCFISH. These products will be based on stakeholder requirements (Gunnlaugsson and Maar, 2025) and requirements for products to be developed in WP3 (New data products and regional database). Data ingestion services for selected new products will be implemented in the AWE of Blue Insight, i.e. packaged as Docker containers that can be run in the AWE to automate fetching and preprocessing of relevant data streams.

To illustrate integration of satellite data products, we ingested an example of a wave data products from the Sentinel-6 satellite. This product was ingested as data points. Other satellite data products provide raster layers, similar to model products shown in this document. Such satellite data products, e.g., for sea surface temperature, will be considered for ingestion in Blue Insight, depending on stakeholder needs.

For the Disko Bay ecosystem model, data products from more years were made available for the Blue Insight platform. Further, ecological indices for fisheries will be developed in WP3 and provided as maps for stakeholders. A new shrimp model will be used to evaluate important areas for the shrimp fishery and to highlight the year-to-year variability under different environmental conditions. The necessary updates of ingestion services for model output will be implemented in parallel with model development.

We have explored ingestion of sample data from the fishing industry, including examples of vessel track data and catch information. Additional fisheries data will be explored together with other relevant data, such as ecosystem and resource management data, to offer new data products. Such products and enhanced Blue Insight services have large potential value for fishing companies, research communities, and resource management and surveillance sectors. Furthermore, Integration of vessel data in NRT into Blue Insight is foreseen. Blue Insight is currently being used in the One Ocean Expedition 2025 – 2026 (<https://www.oneoceanexpedition.com/>) to gather all collected data, making these data available to participants onboard Statsraad Lehmkuhl, and transferring data to NMDC for long-term storage.

9. References

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